

Supplementary information for Robustness increases heritability: implications for familial disease by Steven A. Frank

August 17, 2022

Wolfram Mathematica notebook. PDF version heritable.pdf is a printout of the notebook. Active version heritable.nb can be run under Mathematica software. Created with version 13.1.

Derivation of $g|z$ and test

This section shows the derivation of $g|z$ in the manuscript.

In Mathematica, `NormalDistribution[ $\mu$ ,  $\sigma$ ]` describes a distribution with standard deviation σ . So use standard deviations throughout when defining distributions.

Start with definition $z = g + d$, with g and d independent normal distributions with mean 0 and sd of σg and σd . Then $\text{prob}(g|z)$ begins with $\text{prob}(g|z) = \text{prob}(g \& z) / \text{prob}(z) = \text{prob}(g \& d=z-g) / \text{prob}(z)$. This is equivalent to starting with a Binormal distribution for g and d with zero correlation, evaluating at the point $(g, z-g)$ and dividing by $\text{prob}(z)$ for which $z \sim N(0, \sqrt{\sigma g^2 + \sigma d^2})$.

```
In[ ]:= f[g_, z_,  $\sigma g$ _,  $\sigma d$ _] := PDF[BinormalDistribution[{0, 0}, { $\sigma g$ ,  $\sigma d$ }, 0], {g, z - g}] /  
      PDF[NormalDistribution[0,  $\sqrt{\sigma g^2 + \sigma d^2}$ ], z];
```

```
In[ ]:= Integrate[f[g, z,  $\sigma g$ ,  $\sigma d$ ], {g, - $\infty$ ,  $\infty$ }, Assumptions  $\rightarrow \sigma g > 0 \&\& \sigma d > 0$ ]
```

Out[]:=

1

```
In[ ]:= M1 = Integrate[g * f[g, z,  $\sigma g$ ,  $\sigma d$ ], {g, - $\infty$ ,  $\infty$ }, Assumptions  $\rightarrow \sigma g > 0 \&\& \sigma d > 0$ ];
```

$$\text{mean} = M1 /. \frac{\sigma g^2}{\sigma d^2 + \sigma g^2} \rightarrow h$$

Out[]:=

$h z$

```
In[ ]:= M2 = FullSimplify[  
      Integrate[g^2 * f[g, z,  $\sigma g$ ,  $\sigma d$ ], {g, - $\infty$ ,  $\infty$ }, Assumptions  $\rightarrow \sigma g > 0 \&\& \sigma d > 0$ ]];
```

$$\text{var} = FullSimplify[M2 - M1^2] /. \frac{\sigma g^2}{\sigma d^2 + \sigma g^2} \rightarrow h$$

Out[]:=

$h \sigma d^2$

```
In[*]:= distn = FullSimplify[f[g, z, σg, σd]]
```

```
FullSimplify[distn2 = distn /.  $\frac{\sqrt{\sigma d^2 + \sigma g^2}}{\sigma g} \rightarrow 1/\sqrt{h}$  /.
```

```
(g σd2 + (g - z) σg2)2 → (σd2 + σg2)2 (g - z h)2 /.  $\frac{(\sigma d^2 + \sigma g^2)}{\sigma g^2} \rightarrow 1/h$ ]
```

```
Print["Thus, P(g|z) = ", PDF[NormalDistribution[mean, √var], g],  
", which is N(zh, σd √h) = N(zh, σg √(1-h))."]
```

```
Out[*]=
```

$$\frac{e^{-\frac{(g \sigma d^2 + (g-z) \sigma g^2)^2}{2 \sigma d^2 \sigma g^2 (\sigma d^2 + \sigma g^2)}} \sqrt{\sigma d^2 + \sigma g^2}}{\sqrt{2 \pi} \sigma d \sigma g}$$

```
Out[*]=
```

$$\frac{e^{-\frac{(g-hz)^2}{2 h \sigma d^2}}}{\sqrt{h} \sqrt{2 \pi} \sigma d}$$

Thus, $P(g|z) = \frac{e^{-\frac{(g-hz)^2}{2 h \sigma d^2}}}{\sqrt{2 \pi} \sqrt{h} \sigma d^2}$, which is $N(zh, \sigma d \sqrt{h}) = N(zh, \sigma g \sqrt{1-h})$.

NOTE: $h \sigma d^2 = (1-h) \sigma g^2$

```
In[*]:= fp[g_, z_, σg_, σd_] := PDF[NormalDistribution[z  $\frac{\sigma g^2}{\sigma d^2 + \sigma g^2}$ , σd  $\sqrt{\left(\frac{\sigma g^2}{\sigma d^2 + \sigma g^2}\right)}$ ], g];  
fp2[g_, z_, h_, σd_] := PDF[NormalDistribution[z h, σd √h], g];
```

In[]:=

```
Plot[f[g, 1., 10, 1], {g, -10, 10}, PlotRange -> All]  
Plot[fp[g, 1., 10, 1], {g, -10, 10}, PlotRange -> All]  
Plot[fp2[g, 1., 10 / 11, 1], {g, -10, 10}, PlotRange -> All]
```

Out[]:=

Out[]:=

Out[]:=

Heritability of disease

fyz is y|z with sd rewritten in different form.

$$D = 1 - \text{CDF}[\text{NormalDistribution}[0, \sqrt{(\sigma d^2 + \sigma g^2)}], \text{zstar}] = \frac{1}{2} \text{Erfc}\left[\frac{\text{zstar}}{\sqrt{2} \sqrt{\sigma d^2 + \sigma g^2}}\right]$$

$$\text{In[*]:= } \text{fyz}[y_ , z_ , \sigma g_ , \sigma d_] := \text{PDF}\left[\text{NormalDistribution}\left[z \frac{\sigma g^2}{\sigma d^2 + \sigma g^2}, \sigma d \sqrt{\left(\frac{\sigma g^2}{\sigma d^2 + \sigma g^2} + 1\right)}\right], y\right];$$

$$\text{s1}[z_ , \text{zstar}_ , \sigma g_ , \sigma d_] := \frac{1}{2} \left(1 + \text{Erf}\left[\frac{z \sigma g^2 - \text{zstar} (\sigma d^2 + \sigma g^2)}{\sqrt{2} \sigma d \sqrt{\sigma d^4 + 3 \sigma d^2 \sigma g^2 + 2 \sigma g^4}}\right] \right);$$

$$\text{s2}[\text{zstar}_ , \sigma g_ , \sigma d_] :=$$

$$\text{Log2}\left[\text{NIntegrate}\left[\text{s1}[z, \text{zstar}, \sigma g, \sigma d] * \text{PDF}[\text{NormalDistribution}[0, \sqrt{(\sigma g^2 + \sigma d^2)}], z], \{z, \text{zstar}, \infty\}\right] / \left(\frac{1}{2} \text{Erfc}\left[\frac{\text{zstar}}{\sqrt{2} \sqrt{\sigma d^2 + \sigma g^2}}\right]\right)^2\right];$$

fyz, rearrange sd term

$$\text{In[*]:= } \sigma g^2 (1 - h) + \sigma d^2 /. h \rightarrow \frac{\sigma g^2}{\sigma d^2 + \sigma g^2} /. 1 - \frac{\sigma g^2}{\sigma d^2 + \sigma g^2} \rightarrow \frac{\sigma d^2}{\sigma d^2 + \sigma g^2} /.$$

$$\sigma d^2 + \frac{\sigma d^2 \sigma g^2}{\sigma d^2 + \sigma g^2} \rightarrow \sigma d^2 \left(\frac{\sigma g^2}{\sigma d^2 + \sigma g^2} + 1 \right)$$

Out[*]=

$$\sigma d^2 \left(1 + \frac{\sigma g^2}{\sigma d^2 + \sigma g^2} \right)$$

s1, Prob(y|z > zstar)

$$\text{In[*]:= } \text{FullSimplify}\left[1 - \text{CDF}\left[\text{NormalDistribution}\left[z \frac{\sigma g^2}{\sigma d^2 + \sigma g^2}, \sigma d \sqrt{\left(\frac{\sigma g^2}{\sigma d^2 + \sigma g^2} + 1\right)}\right], \text{zstar}\right]\right]$$

Out[*]=

$$\frac{1}{2} \left(1 + \text{Erf}\left[\frac{-\text{zstar} + \frac{z \sigma g^2}{\sigma d^2 + \sigma g^2}}{\sigma d \sqrt{2 + \frac{2 \sigma g^2}{\sigma d^2 + \sigma g^2}}}\right] \right)$$

Now, take numerator and denominator of Erf[] separately, multiplying each by $\sigma d^2 + \sigma g^2$

$$\text{In[*]:= } \text{Simplify}\left[\left(-\text{zstar} + \frac{z \sigma g^2}{\sigma d^2 + \sigma g^2}\right) (\sigma d^2 + \sigma g^2)\right]$$

Out[*]=

$$z \sigma g^2 - \text{zstar} (\sigma d^2 + \sigma g^2)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{In[*]:= } & \sigma d \sqrt{2 + \frac{2 \sigma g^2}{\sigma d^2 + \sigma g^2}} (\sigma d^2 + \sigma g^2) /. \sqrt{2 + \frac{2 \sigma g^2}{\sigma d^2 + \sigma g^2}} \rightarrow \sqrt{2} \sqrt{\frac{\sigma d^2 + 2 \sigma g^2}{\sigma d^2 + \sigma g^2}} /. \\
 & (\sigma d^2 + \sigma g^2) \sqrt{\frac{\sigma d^2 + 2 \sigma g^2}{\sigma d^2 + \sigma g^2}} \rightarrow \sqrt{(\sigma d^2 + \sigma g^2) (\sigma d^2 + 2 \sigma g^2)} /. \\
 & \sqrt{(\sigma d^2 + \sigma g^2) (\sigma d^2 + 2 \sigma g^2)} \rightarrow \sqrt{\sigma d^4 + 3 \sigma d^2 \sigma g^2 + 2 \sigma g^4} \\
 \text{Out[*]:= } & \sqrt{2} \sigma d \sqrt{\sigma d^4 + 3 \sigma d^2 \sigma g^2 + 2 \sigma g^4}
 \end{aligned}$$

Probability of disease, D

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{In[*]:= } & 1 - \text{CDF}[\text{NormalDistribution}[0, \sqrt{(\sigma d^2 + \sigma g^2)}], \text{zstar}] \\
 \text{Out[*]:= } & 1 - \frac{1}{2} \text{Erfc}\left[-\frac{\text{zstar}}{\sqrt{2} \sqrt{\sigma d^2 + \sigma g^2}}\right] \\
 \text{In[*]:= } & \text{FullSimplify}\left[1 - \frac{1}{2} \text{Erfc}\left[-\frac{\text{zstar}}{\sqrt{2} \sqrt{\sigma d^2 + \sigma g^2}}\right]\right] == \frac{1}{2} \text{Erfc}\left[\frac{\text{zstar}}{\sqrt{2} \sqrt{\sigma d^2 + \sigma g^2}}\right] \\
 \text{Out[*]:= } & \text{True}
 \end{aligned}$$

Graphics

```

In[*]:= T = Table[Null, {i, 2}, {j, 3}];
For[z = 1, z ≤ 2, z++,
  For[σg = 1, σg ≤ 3, σg++,
    T[[z, σg]] = Table[{σd, s2[z * √(σg² + σd²), σg, σd]}, {σd, .2, 5, .2}];
  ];
];
Clear[z, σg, σd];

```

```

In[ ]:= dcolor = ColorData[97, "ColorList"];
xticks = {0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5};
yticks = Table[{i, ToString[2^i]}, {i, 0, 5}];
origin = -0.3;
p1 = ListPlot[T[[1]], Joined → True, PlotRange → {origin, 5.6},
  AxesOrigin → {0, origin}, Ticks → {xticks, yticks}];
p2 = ListPlot[T[[2]], Joined → True, PlotRange → {origin, 5.6},
  Axes → {True, False}, AxesOrigin → {0, origin}, Ticks → {xticks, None}];
gr = GraphicsRow[{p1, p2}, Spacings → 5, ImagePadding → {{11, 0}, {15, 0}},
  Epilog → {
    Inset[Text[Style["(a)", FontSize → 11]], ImageScaled[{0.085, 0.92}]],
    Inset[Text[Style["(b)", FontSize → 11]], ImageScaled[{0.525, 0.92}]],
    Inset[Text[Style["z* =  $\sigma_z$ ; disease freq = 0.16", FontSize → 11]],
      ImageScaled[{0.298, 0.97}]],
    Inset[Text[Style["z* =  $2\sigma_z$ ; disease freq = 0.023", FontSize → 11]],
      ImageScaled[{0.798, 0.97}]],
    Inset[Text[Style[" $\sigma_g = 2$ ", FontSize → 11]], ImageScaled[{0.400, 0.67}]],
    Inset[Text[Style["3", FontSize → 11]], ImageScaled[{0.4212, 0.75}]],
    Inset[Text[Style["1", FontSize → 11]], ImageScaled[{0.422, 0.59}]],
    Inset[Graphics[{Thick, , dcolor[[3]], Line[{{0.6, 0}, {0.75, 0}]}]],
      ImageScaled[{0.452, 0.75}]],
    Inset[Graphics[{Thick, , dcolor[[2]], Line[{{0.6, 0}, {0.75, 0}]}]],
      ImageScaled[{0.452, 0.675}]],
    Inset[Graphics[{Thick, dcolor[[1]], Line[{{0.6, 0}, {0.75, 0}]}]],
      ImageScaled[{0.452, 0.59}]],
    Inset[Text[Style["Developmental standard deviation,  $\sigma_d$ ", FontSize → 16]],
      ImageScaled[{0.5, 0.05}]],
    Rotate[Inset[Text[Style["Disease heritability, H'", FontSize → 14]],
      ImageScaled[{0.0115, 0.55}]], 90 Degree]}]
Export["/Users/steve/Desktop/gr.pdf", gr];

```

Out[]:=

Disease frequency for $z^* = \sigma_z$

```
In[*]:= Clear[z, σg, σd];
1 - CDF[NormalDistribution[0, √(σg2 + σd2)], z √(σg2 + σd2)] /. z → 1.
```

```
Out[*]=
0.158655
```

Disease frequency for $z^* = x * \sigma_z$

```
In[*]:= 1 - CDF[NormalDistribution[0, √(σg2 + σd2)], z √(σg2 + σd2)] /. z → x
```

```
Out[*]=
1 -  $\frac{1}{2}$  Erfc[- $\frac{x}{\sqrt{2}}$ ]
```

Different forms of robustness: consequences

General functions and setup

```
fitness[x_, m_, V_] := Exp[-(x - m)2 / (2 V)]
fitnessDI[x_, m_, V_, σd_] :=
Integrate[fitness[z, m, V] * PDF[NormalDistribution[x, σd], z],
{z, -∞, ∞}, Assumptions → σd > 0 && V > 0]
```

```
In[*]:= fitnessDI[g, m, V, σd]
Out[*]=
```

$$e^{-\frac{(g-m)^2}{2(V+\sigma_d^2)}} \sqrt{\frac{V}{V+\sigma_d^2}}$$

w|g, fitness given genetic value, g

```
In[*]:= fitnessD[g_, m_, V_, σd_] := e^{-\frac{(g-m)^2}{2(V+\sigma_d^2)}}
gVar[c_, μ_, V_, σd_] := Sqrt[c2 μ (V + σd2)]
```

For Lande's Gaussian approx for genetic variance need $\mu \gg \frac{c^2}{2(V+\sigma_d^2)}$ or $\log_{10}\left(\frac{2\mu(V+\sigma_d^2)}{c^2}\right) > 1$

```
In[*]:= testG[c_, μ_, V_, σd_] := Log10[2 μ (V + σd2) / c2]
```

Case I: decrease selective intensity (raise V)

```
In[*]:= h[c_, μ_, V_, σd_] := gVar[c, μ, V, σd] / (gVar[c, μ, V, σd] + σd2)
```

In[*]:= **h[c, μ, V, σd]**

Out[*]=

$$\frac{\sqrt{c^2 \mu (V + \sigma d^2)}}{\sigma d^2 + \sqrt{c^2 \mu (V + \sigma d^2)}}$$

In[*]:= **h[c, μ, V, σd]**

Out[*]=

$$\frac{\sqrt{c^2 \mu (V + \sigma d^2)}}{\sigma d^2 + \sqrt{c^2 \mu (V + \sigma d^2)}}$$

Case II: decrease developmental variance ($dh/d\sigma d^2 < 0$)

In[*]:= **FullSimplify[D[h[c, μ, V, σd] /. σd² → d, d] /. d → σd²]**

Out[*]=

$$-\frac{c^2 \mu (2V + \sigma d^2)}{2 \sqrt{c^2 \mu (V + \sigma d^2)} (\sigma d^2 + \sqrt{c^2 \mu (V + \sigma d^2)})^2}$$

Case of $\mu \gg s$

Graphic for general heritability, $\mu \gg s$

```

In[ ]:= xticks = Table[{i, ToString[i]}, {i, 0.0, 1.0, 0.2}];
yticks = Table[{i, ToString[i]}, {i, 0.2, 1.0, 0.2}];
c = 0.1;
 $\mu = 10^{-4}$ ;
V =  $10^2$ ;
g1 = Plot[{h[c,  $\mu$ , V,  $\sigma d$ ], h[c,  $\mu$ , ( $10^{0.5}$ ) V,  $\sigma d$ ], h[c,  $\mu$ , 10 V,  $\sigma d$ ]},
  { $\sigma d$ , 0, 1}, PlotRange -> {0, 1}, Ticks -> {xticks, yticks}]
Print["testG at  $\sigma d = 0$ : ", testG[c,  $\mu$ , {V, ( $10^{0.5}$ ) V, 10 V}, 0]]
Print["testG at  $\sigma d = 1$ : ", testG[c,  $\mu$ , {V, ( $10^{0.5}$ ) V, 10 V}, 1]]
Print["zstar: ", -Log[0.9] Sqrt[{V, ( $10^{0.5}$ ) V, 10 V} / 2]]
Plot[{testG[c,  $\mu$ , V,  $\sigma d$ ]}, { $\sigma d$ , 0, 1}, PlotRange -> {0, Automatic}];
Clear[c,  $\mu$ ,  $\sigma d$ ];

```

Out[]:=

testG at $\sigma d = 0$: {0.30103, 0.80103, 1.30103}

testG at $\sigma d = 1$: {0.305351, 0.802401, 1.30146}

zstar: {0.745011, 1.32484, 2.35593}

Heritability of disease, $\mu \gg s$

```

In[ ]:= zstar[ $\gamma$ _, V_] := -Log[ $\gamma$ ] Sqrt[V / 2];
hod[ $\gamma$ _, c_,  $\mu$ _, V_,  $\sigma d$ _] := s2[zstar[ $\gamma$ , V], Sqrt[gVar[c,  $\mu$ , V,  $\sigma d$ ]],  $\sigma d$ ];

In[ ]:= hod[0.9, 0.1,  $10^{-4}$ ,  $10^2$ , .5]
Out[ ]:=
0.196139

```

```

In[ ]:= xticks = Table[{i, ToString[i]}, {i, 0.0, 1.0, 0.2}];
        yticks = Table[{i, ToString[2^i]}, {i, 1, 5}];

         $\gamma$  = 0.9;
        c = 0.1;
         $\mu$  =  $10^{-4}$ ;
        V =  $10^2$ ;
        g2 = Plot[{hod[ $\gamma$ , c,  $\mu$ , V,  $\sigma$ ], hod[ $\gamma$ , c,  $\mu$ , ( $10^{0.5}$ ) V,  $\sigma$ ], hod[ $\gamma$ , c,  $\mu$ , 10 V,  $\sigma$ ]},
                { $\sigma$ , 0.03, 1}, PlotRange -> {0, 5}, Ticks -> {xticks, yticks}]
        Clear[ $\gamma$ , c,  $\mu$ , V,  $\sigma$ ];

```



```

In[ ]:= dcolor = ColorData[97, "ColorList"];
gr = GraphicsRow[{g1, g2}, Spacings -> 45, ImagePadding -> {{0, 0}, {15, 0}},
  Epilog -> {
    Inset[Text[Style["(a)", FontSize -> 11]], ImageScaled[{0.125, 0.92}]],
    Inset[Text[Style["(b)", FontSize -> 11]], ImageScaled[{0.585, 0.92}]],
    Inset[Text[Style["log10 V = 2.5", FontSize -> 11]], ImageScaled[{0.300, 0.67}]],
    Inset[Text[Style["3.0", FontSize -> 11]], ImageScaled[{0.3392, 0.75}]],
    Inset[Text[Style["2.0", FontSize -> 11]], ImageScaled[{0.340, 0.59}]],
    Inset[Graphics[{Thick, , dcolor[[3]], Line[{{0.6, 0}, {0.75, 0}]}]],
      ImageScaled[{0.382, 0.75}]],
    Inset[Graphics[{Thick, , dcolor[[2]], Line[{{0.6, 0}, {0.75, 0}]}]],
      ImageScaled[{0.382, 0.675}]],
    Inset[Graphics[{Thick, dcolor[[1]], Line[{{0.6, 0}, {0.75, 0}]}]],
      ImageScaled[{0.382, 0.59}]],
    Inset[Text[Style["Developmental standard deviation, σd", FontSize -> 16]],
      ImageScaled[{0.5, 0.05}]],
    Rotate[Inset[Text[Style["Heritability, h", FontSize -> 14]],
      ImageScaled[{0.0215, 0.55}]], 90 Degree],
    Rotate[Inset[Text[Style["Disease heritability, H'", FontSize -> 14]],
      ImageScaled[{0.5170, 0.55}]], 90 Degree]]]
Export["/Users/steve/Desktop/gr.pdf", gr];

```

Out[]:=

Case of $\mu \ll s$

Use of Gaussian throughout following for all calculations may not be accurate here, however Gaussians provide a reasonable way to study qualitative trends and very rough approximations. Conclusion is that qualitative trends are same as for stronger selection relative to mutation, but overall heritabilities are somewhat smaller. To evaluate further, should scale all phenotypic consequences to smaller scaling, $\sqrt{V}$, for relation between phenotypes and fitness, associated with stronger selection.

Heritability of disease, $\mu \ll s$

```
In[ ]:= gVar2[μ_, V_, σd_] := 2 μ (V + σd2)
h2[c_, μ_, V_, σd_] := gVar2[μ, V, σd] / (gVar2[μ, V, σd] + σd2)
```

Graphic for general heritability, $\mu \ll s$

```
In[ ]:= c = 1.;
μ = 10-4;
V = 101.5;
Plot[{h2[c, μ, V, σd], h2[c, μ, (100.5) V, σd], h2[c, μ, 10 V, σd]},
{σd, 0, 1}, PlotRange → {0, 1}]
Print["testG at σd = 0: ", testG[c, μ, {V, (100.5) V, 10 V}, 0]]
Print["testG at σd = 1: ", testG[c, μ, {V, (100.5) V, 10 V}, 1]]
Print["zstar: ", -Log[0.9] Sqrt[{V, (100.5) V, 10 V} / 2]]
Plot[{testG[c, μ, V, σd]}, {σd, 0, 1}, PlotRange → {0, Automatic}];
Clear[c, μ, σd];
```

Out[]:=

testG at $\sigma d = 0$: {-2.19897, -1.69897, -1.19897}

testG at $\sigma d = 1$: {-2.18545, -1.69465, -1.1976}

zstar: {0.418951, 0.745011, 1.32484}

Heritability of disease, $\mu \ll s$

```
In[ ]:= hod2[γ_, c_, μ_, V_, σd_] := s2[zstar[γ, V], Sqrt[gVar2[μ, V, σd]], σd];
```

```

In[ ]:=  $\gamma = 0.9;$ 
         $c = 1.;$ 
         $\mu = 10^{-4};$ 
         $V = 10^{1.5};$ 
        Plot[{hod2[ $\gamma$ , c,  $\mu$ , V,  $\sigma$ ], hod2[ $\gamma$ , c,  $\mu$ , (100.5) V,  $\sigma$ ], hod2[ $\gamma$ , c,  $\mu$ , 10 V,  $\sigma$ ]},
            { $\sigma$ , 0.03, 1}, PlotRange -> {0, 5}]
        Clear[ $\gamma$ , c,  $\mu$ , V,  $\sigma$ ];

```



```

In[ ]:= zstar[0.9, {10, 100}]

```

```

Out[ ]:= {0.235593, 0.745011}

```